

Pediatric physical therapy course importance: Relating to internship practice

Naizel-Lyn P. De Guzman*, Harry S. Canaba, Rebecca Ruth Baliga
School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: naizellyn.deguzman@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Pediatric physical therapy is a branch of physical therapy that deals with various health issues affecting medical disorders in children. To align with the society's demands, the Physical Therapy Department of St. Dominic College of Asia has evolved its educational curriculum. Through this, the internship program is an act of imparting, improving or updating knowledge and skills of students which they learn in the form of theory. 11 interns (respondents) participated and answered the online survey form to give us a hint if there is a huge impact of adding a specialized course such as Pediatric PT in BSPT curriculum in their clinical training. Physical therapists handling or specializing in children may benefit from the use of evidence-informed practice to provide any of the following services as part of their goal-directed plan of care.

Keywords: *Pediatric physical therapy course; Internship practice; Students.*

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Introduction

Pediatric physical therapy is a branch of physical therapy that deals with various health issues affecting medical disorders in children. The pediatric physical therapist works hand in hand with children and their families to help every child attain their maximum potential to function independently and to promote active participation in home, school, and community environments (AAPT, 2019). Children with autism spectrum disorders, cerebral palsy, Down's syndrome, muscular dystrophy, arthrogryposis, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, spina bifida, cystic fibrosis, and traumatic brain injury are just few of the conditions that the physical therapist for children deals with (BrightMinds Speech and Occupational Therapy Center, 2019; Hilton et al., 2019). In addition, pediatric physical therapy is involved in correcting posture, gait, balance and coordination of children by improving their quality of life (Blauw-Hospers et al., 2011).

According to the World Confederation for Physical Therapy (WCPT) guidelines (2011), there are four major patient management skills that entry-level PT should possess such as examination, evaluation, diagnosis and prognosis, and intervention. Under the guidance of a clinical teacher, an intern learns to combine and integrate the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values as well as the philosophies of the profession during the transition from a PT student to a competent therapist (Ernstzen et al., 2009). However, to align with the society's demands for the 21st century workforce, school districts and higher educational institutions have begun "curriculum revisions" of their institutional and internship programs (Johnson, 2001).

In line with the advancement of teaching and learning in the 21st century, the Physical Therapy Department of St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) has evolved its educational curriculum from an old to the new curriculum in its effort to align its students and alumni to be globally competitive in learning and skills development with up-to-date learning based on current and evidenced based practices and developments. The pediatric physical therapy course is one of the additions in the new curriculum in physical therapy. This research involved Level 5 old

curriculum interns (no pediatric PT course) and Level 4 new curriculum interns (with pediatric PT course).

As PT practitioners of more than five (5) years, who handled many pediatric patients with different conditions, the authors can say that pediatric patients are one of those challenging populations to handle. There are a lot of factors that a person has to consider and expect when treating a pediatric patient. As what researchers observed among the particular population mentioned above, attention span and mood are just a couple of those factors that may make the treatment session even harder other than the fact that we have different levels of understanding.

Methodology

This study has to be done the easiest possible way to avoid facing other challenges. An online survey form was sent to a group chat and relayed to current physical therapy interns of SDCA with Level 5 old curriculum and Level 4 new curriculum interns. The survey consists of a series of questions pertaining to the importance of pediatric courses relating to their internship practice.

11 interns (respondents) participated and answered the online survey form, and the illustration of their responses are shown below. Data was collected and gathered, which would determine if there were truly an impact or even a slight difference if a specialization course, particularly in pediatric PT, is needed in the curriculum of the students.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Internship level

72.7% of the respondents are categorized as level 5 old curriculum, while 27.3% of the respondents were from the level 4 curriculum. According to Jogan and Sushma (2019), the internship program is an act of imparting, improving or updating knowledge and skills of students which they learn in the form of theory. It permits them to understand the connection between theory and practice thus enhancing the students' knowledge of their potential to reach the goals set for various professions.

Figure 2. Number of months of duty in clinic / facility as intern

As the data reflects, 54.5% of the respondents have gone through more than six (6) months of their clinical training, while 45.5% have less. Based on the Memorandum Order Number 55 series of 2017 about policies and guidelines for the BSPT education issued by the Commission on Higher Education, interns must undergo training under the supervision of a licensed PT with a minimum of 1500 hours (Licuanan, 2017; Bautista et al., 2020). The number of training months is important especially to any medical or healthcare practitioners in enhancing skills. Experience would teach the clinician so much particularly in the decision making.

Figure 3. Pediatric physical therapy course included in curriculum

54.5% of the students said that the Pediatric PT course is included in their curriculum, which implies that there is really a need for this particular course to be incorporated into their skills. According to APTA Academy of Pediatric Physical Therapy (2019), physical therapists handling or specializing in children may benefit the use of evidence-informed practice to provide any of the following services as part of their goal-directed plan of care: Developmental activities, movement and mobility, strengthening, motor learning, balance and coordination, recreation, play, and leisure, daily care activities and routines, equipment design, fabrication, and fitting, tone management, and some others.

Figure 4. PT interns handling pediatric cases

When researchers asked the respondents if they have handled a pediatric case during their internship, 81.8% mentioned that they have, and 20% implied they have not. The numbers above show that most of intern respondents from both old and new curriculum have handled pediatric cases. Having said that, those with pediatric PT course interns may have come across with a more familiar case than those who did not have.

Figure 5. Familiarity with pediatric cases

There were 72.7% of interns who indicated that the pediatric cases they handled were familiar to them, while 18.2% said that they were not familiar with some of the cases, and 9.1% implied it is not applicable to them. Case familiarity is important to be able to handle properly and address the needs of the patient during treatment sessions. In the article of Gatej et al. (2020) discussing clinicians' knowledge with the guidelines of handling children with behavioral problems, it appeared in their study that under half of the clinicians reported being unaware of guidelines. Unfamiliarity with those guidelines and protocols may end up in catastrophe.

Respondents also have given several skills which they used, but the authors preferred to narrow it down to the most important ones that must be learned by any healthcare professional which may encounter children in their practice. The following skills were recognized by the interns:

1. Communication skills
2. Flexibility
3. Interpersonal skills
4. Patience
5. Critical thinking and clinical judgment

These are just some of the critical skills to know in handling all patients, but mastery of the mentioned skills will assist the clinician in dealing with children. As per Clark (2020), pediatric patients need different communication methods to have a positive experience, since most of the time they are afraid or nervous which makes their parents feel stressed just like the patients. Some of our respondents confirmed it as they implied that it can be a difficult situation to handle as a healthcare provider. Flexibility, on the other hand, can be very handy. It is imperative that all practitioners must be adoptable with the environment, the situation and most of all with the people surrounding them. This is relevant to their interpersonal skills. Regardless of the size and shape and societal status of the patient, it is the patient's right to be treated properly.

Patience is one human trait that is necessary if a person is a physical therapist. And in handling pediatric patients, PTs would require even more of it. For more than a decade of clinical experience, different situations have occurred during PT sessions which tested the patience of physical therapists. Those occasions impacted them greatly to learn to extend patience. Handling

children can be really challenging if a PT is impatient. Critical thinking is one of the important skills any healthcare provider can have. It is necessary to keep enhancing this skill to assure the safety of any patient, which is the foremost goal.

The respondents were then asked to list down different challenges they encountered in handling a pediatric case. Below are the actual answers the interns indicated.

PT1: *The three challenges are building trust, communication, and pressure.*

PT2: *For me, I encountered the severity, tantrums, and the teletherapy itself.*

PT3: *I have experienced unexpected tantrums of the patient.*

PT4: *The child throws tantrums.*

PT5: *Parent or guardian does not understand the activity.*

PT6: *Incorporating play into the exercises is challenging.*

PT7: *Handling through tele-rehab is difficult as we are not totally handling the patients in person.*

PT8: *There are many times that I was not able to follow my treatment plan due to many factors such as the patient's mood, progression, and regression. Sometimes the parents or guardian of the patient was not cooperative with us. Documentation including tele-rehab setting is hard, especially in calming a physical therapist.*

PT9: *Pediatric patients quickly lose their attention so as the physical therapist. We need to exert more effort and patience in handling our pediatric patients and give the best quality of life.*

PT10: *Some are not following instructions because their attention is to play all day as a result of not responding to treatment.*

PT11: *Theoretically, the whole specialty itself. And the fact that we handled it via tele-rehab.*

As observed, there were several times tantrums have been mentioned. This is a normal attitude a child patient exhibits during a PT session. This must be expected by our respondents on their next encounter with a pediatric patient; thus, different strategies to diminish the attitude may be adopted, learned and utilized since it will help to have a smooth session flow.

There are also a couple of notes of parent's reaction to the session. It is necessary to involve the parents in all treatment protocols since they are the ones who have the strongest connection with the patient. However, circumstances were encountered as what were stated by the respondents such that some parents do not understand the activity, and some were uncooperative.

A healthcare provider must always need to make sure to use understandable words. As per Clark (2020), it is still important using basic terms with their parents since even many adults are unable to identify medical terms. Additionally, engaging the parents in conversations during treatment sessions will make children to be more relaxed because they seek for their parents' guidance, the ones who they trust (Clark, 2020).

Intern respondents have done assessment and treatment through tele-rehab. During this pandemic, telemedicine has become more popular. Tele-rehab is a subset of it, where conducting evaluation, consultation, therapy, and monitoring to provide rehabilitation care for patients in various locations, such as home, community, nearby health facility, and workplace are being delivered remotely through an electronic technology. This tele-rehab setup has doubled the challenge of the PT interns in handling pediatric patients. Additionally, as it was noted, there is no guideline on telerehabilitation principles, scope of services, procedure, and regulations that can be applicable across various rehabilitation professional organizations in the country (Leochico, 2020).

Conclusion

Those respondents who indicated that they were practicing for about less than 5 months have more opportunities to encounter pediatric cases and practice. It was clear that there were challenges encountered when handling pediatric patients. But skill enhancement will not stop after internship. The career itself is a whole world to keep enhancing any skill. Pediatric patients are really challenging to handle; thus, we can safely say that having advanced knowledge like acquiring information through adding specialized courses in the curriculum is vital since it will make it easier for the interns to handle them in their practicum.

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